

Amperometric Study on the Polyvanadates of Lead and the Determination of Vanadium (V) as Lead Pyrovanadate

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The stoichiometry of the compounds formed by the interaction of lead salt and different alkali-vanadates (ortho-, pyro, meta and poly) have been investigated by means of amperometric titrations between the reactants at $E_{d.c.} = -0.8$ Vs. S.C.E. The end points obtained from the sharp breaks in titration curves provide definite evidence for the formation and precipitation of ortho— $3\text{PbO}\cdot\text{V}_2\text{O}_6$, pyro- $2\text{PbO}\cdot\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ and meta $\text{PbO}\cdot\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ vanadates of lead at $p\text{H}$ ranges 7.5–9.0, 5.75–7.25 and 4.25–5.25 respectively. The precipitation of lead-pyrovanadate has been found to be quantitative and the amperometric titrations offer a simple and rapid method for the determination of vanadium (V) in solutions at suitable concentrations and $p\text{H}$ ranges.

The literature on the study of vanadates of lead is scanty and most of the earlier workers had confined themselves to the preparative and analytical study of these compounds. H. E. Roscoe¹ prepared sparingly soluble lead ortho-vanadate $\text{Pb}_3(\text{VO}_4)_2$ by adding lead acetate to sodium ortho-vanadate solution. F. Ephraim and G. Beck² reported the formation of lead ortho-hexavanadate $3\text{PbO}\cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by treating manganese hexavanadate with lead nitrate. J. J. Berzelius³ obtained the yellow precipitate of lead deutero-tetra-vanadate $\text{PbV}_4\text{O}_{11}$. A Ditte⁴ prepared lead pyro-vanadate $\text{Pb}_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_7$ by pouring ammonium meta-vanadate solution into an acetic-acid solution of lead nitrate. H. E. Roscoe (*Loc. cit*) on mixing sodium pyro vanadate and lead acetate solutions, obtained lead oxypyro-vanadate $\text{PbO}\cdot 2\text{Pb}_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_7$; possibly a mixture of $\text{Pb}_3(\text{VO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Pb}_2\text{V}_2\text{O}_7$. A Carnot⁵, V. L. Zolotavin⁶ and Henri Guiter⁷ reported the formation of lead meta vanadates under different conditions. In view of the insufficient and conflicting details of the reports of earlier workers on the compositions of lead vanadates, and in the absence of any electro-metric data on the subject, it was considered worthwhile to study the formation and composition of lead vanadates, obtained by the interaction of lead nitrate and alkali vanadates at different $p\text{H}$ levels, by means of electrometric techniques which have provided more conclusive evidences on the composition of vanadates of metals^{8–12}. The results of amperometric studies on this system have been presented in this communication.

1. H. E. Roscoe, *Phil. Trans.*, 1868, 158, 1; *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1868, 16, 220; 1870, 18, 37, 313; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1868, 21, 322.
2. F. Ephraim, and G. Beck., *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1926, 9, 38.
3. J. J. Berzelius, *Acad. Handl. Stockholm.*, 1831, 1.; *Schweigger's Jour.*, 1831, 62, 323; *Pogg. Ann.*, 1831, 22, 1.
4. A. Ditte, *Compt. Rend.*, 1883, 96, 1050, 121; 1887, 104, 1707.
5. A. Carnot, *Compt. Rend.*, 1887, 105, 121.
6. V. L. Zolotavin, *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1947, 2, 364.
7. H. Guiter, *Ann. Chim.*, 1941, 15, 5.
8. R. S. Saxena, and O. P. Sharma, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, 28, 195.
9. R. S. Saxena, and M. L. Mittal, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 2553.
10. R. S. Saxena, and O. P. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 5, 9.
11. R. S. Saxena, and M. L. Mittal, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 125.
12. R. S. Saxena, and O. P. Sharma, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 209.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anal.R. (B.D.H.) reagents, NaOH, V_2O_5 , $Pb(NO_3)_2$, gelatin and reagent grade HNO_3 were used and their solutions prepared in air free conductivity water.

A Cambridge General purpose polarograph with scalamp galvanometer was used for performing amperometric titrations. A dropping mercury electrode having the following characteristics, $m = 2.416$ mg/sec, $t = 3.5$ sec, and $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.226$ $mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}$ at $E_{d.e.} = -1.0$ V (vs. S.C.E.) was used in conjunction with saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by low resistance salt bridge. All amperometric titrations were performed at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ in presence of 20% alcoholic medium using 0.1 M KNO_3 as supporting electrolyte and 0.01% gelatin as maximum suppressor at an applied potential of -0.8 V (vs S.C.E.) which is the limiting current plateau potential of the wave produced by Pb^{2+} ions. Twenty ml of the titre solution was taken in the cell each time, it was swept and stirred by bubbling pure nitrogen. After each addition of the titrant, the observed current was corrected for the dilution effect and plotted against the volume of titrant added. The end point was located graphically.

The standard solution of alkali ortho-vanadate was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of vanadium pentoxide in the calculated quantity of boiling solution of NaOH of the required strength. Alkali pyro, meta and poly-vanadate solutions were then prepared by adding required quantity of HNO_3 at 100° . Employing different concentrations of alkali vanadates and lead nitrate, amperometric titrations were carried out with each of the reagents alternately used as the titrant. Only two figures (1 and 2) illustrating direct and reverse titrations of each type have been given for the sake of brevity and the results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE I
Summary of the results of Amperometric titrations

Molarity of solutions		Equivalent points (ml.).	
		Calculated	Observed
$Pb(NO_3)_2$	$3NaO.V_2O_5$	Direct Ortho-vanadate Titrations, (fig. 1, curve-A.)	
M/5	M/100	3.0	3.0
M/30	M/500	3.60	3.60
M/100	M/1500	4.0	4.05
		Reverse titrations, (fig. 2, curve-A)	
M/20	M/10	3.33	3.35
M/200	M/80	2.66	2.65
M/1000	M/600	4.0	4.05
$Pb(NO_3)_2$	$2Na_2O.V_2O_5$	Direct Pyro-vanadate titrations, (fig. 1, curve-B)	
M/10	M/125	3.20	3.20
M/50	M/500	4.0	4.0
M/60	M/800	3.0	2.95
M/100	M/1500	2.66	2.60
		Reverse titrations (fig. 2, curve-B)	
M/100	M/30	3.0	3.0
M/400	M/125	3.2	3.15
M/800	M/200	2.5	2.55
M/1000	M/400	4.0	3.95
$Pb(NO_3)_2$	$Na_2O.V_2O_5$	Direct Meta-vanadate titrations (fig. 1, curve-C)	
M/10	M/50	4.0	4.0
M/50	M/300	3.33	3.30
M/100	M/800	2.50	2.55
		Reverse titrations (fig. 2, curve-C)	
M/150	M/25	3.33	3.35
M/800	M/100	2.5	2.5
M/1600	M/250	3.12	3.10

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The vanadate anion (VO_4^{3-}) in acid medium shows anomalous behaviour and forms different isopoly anions of varying compositions through a series of intermediate steps. The systematic electrometric investigations carried out by Saxena and Coworkers¹³⁻¹⁵ on such systems have shown the formation of three different poly-anions viz., pyro- $(\text{V}_2\text{O}_7)^{4-}$, meta- $(\text{VO}_3)^{1-}$ and poly- $(\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{27})^{4-}$ in the vicinity of pH 10, 7 and 4.5 respectively. With a view to ascertaining whether these poly-anions form the corresponding heavy metal derivatives, the reaction between alkali vanadates and lead (II) has been studied by amperometric titrations with regard to the changes occurring in H^+ ion concentrations and the composition of the precipitates formed.

Fig. 1. Direct amperometric titrations between $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and Sodium vanadates.

Curve-A. ml of M/5 $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added to 20 ml of M/100 $3\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$.

Curve-B. ml of M/10 $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added to 20 ml of M/125 $2\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$.

Curve-C. ml of M/10 $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added to 20 ml of M/50 $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$.

Ortho-vanadate titrations : Using different concentrations of lead nitrate and sodium ortho-vanadate, a series of amperometric titrations were carried out at $E_{a.e.} = -0.8 \text{ V}$ at which Pb^{2+} ions give well-defined reduction wave, while vanadate ion does not produce any measurable diffusion current. In the direct titrations (fig. 1, curve A), when ortho-vanadate solution is used as the titre, the observed current of the magnitude of few microamperes remains almost unchanged on the addition of lead nitrate solution till the stoichiometric end point is reached and after which the diffusion current due to Pb^{2+} ions increases linearly with the addition of the latter. In the case of inverse titrations when lead nitrate solution is used as the titre (fig. 2, curve A), reverse phenomenon is observed. Well-defined

13. R. S. Saxena, and O. P. Sharma, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1881.

14. R. S. Saxena, and M. L. Mittal, *Acta. Chim. Hung.*, 1964, **40**, 109.

15. R. S. Saxena, and M. L. Mittal, *Naturwiss.*, 1964, **51**, 1.

breaks are obtained in the titration curves at a point where the molecular ratio of $\text{PbO} : \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ is 3 : 1 and suggest the formation of lead ortho-vanadate having the composition $3\text{PbO} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ at pH range (7.5–9.5), according to the following equation :

Pyro-vanadate titrations : The solution of sodium pyro-vanadate was prepared as described earlier and its reaction with lead salt studied by performing amperometric titrations. The end points obtained from the titration curves (figs. 1 and 2, curve B) indicate

Fig. 2. Reverse Amperometric titrations between $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and Sodium vanadates.

Curve-A. ml of M/80 $3\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ added to 20 ml of M/200 $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

Curve-B. ml of M/30 $2\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ added to 20 ml of M/100 $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

Curve-C. ml of M/25 $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ added to 20 ml of M/150 $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

that Pb^{2+} and $\text{V}_2\text{O}_4^{4-}$ ions combine in the ratio of 2 : 1 suggesting the formation of lead pyro-vanadate $2\text{PbO} \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ at pH range 5.75–7.25.

The accuracy and reproducibility of pyro-vanadate titrations have been found to be excellent even at considerably low dilutions of reactants and the titrimetric procedure seems to offer a simple and rapid method of determining vanadium (V) as lead pyro-vanadate (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Amperometric determination of Vanadium (V) as lead pyro-vanadate

Vanadium (V) present (gms/litre).	0.815	0.205	0.127	0.068
Vanadium (V) found (gms/litre).	0.815	0.205	0.125	0.066

Meta-vanadate titrations : The amperometric titrations performed between lead nitrate and sodium meta-vanadate solutions yield well defined breaks (figs. 1 and 2, curve C) at a point where the ratio of reacting species $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ is as 1 : 1, which corresponds to the formation of lead meta-vanadate— $\text{PbO}\cdot\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ at pH range 4.25–5.25 and can be expressed as follows :

The reaction between $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and alkali poly-vanadate ($\text{Na}_2\text{O}\cdot 2.5 \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$) solutions was studied but no precipitation of lead polyvanadate occurred and hence the titrations did not yield any break which could throw light on the formation and composition of lead polyvanadate.

It is observed that after each addition of the titrant solution, it takes a little time for the current values to become steady. Thorough stirring in the vicinity of the end point has favourable effect.

The present investigations confirm the formation and precipitation of 3 $\text{PbO}\cdot\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$, 2 $\text{PbO}\cdot\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{PbO}\cdot\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ at pH ranges 7.5–9.5, 5.75–7.25 and 4.25–5.25 respectively.

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